

MEASUREMENT OF FAILURE PROCESS OF SINGLE FILAMENT EMBEDDED IN RESIN MATRIX BY USING A FIBER-OPTIC STRAIN RATE SENSOR

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SUMMARY: The authors have developed a new fiber-optic strain rate sensor based on Doppler effect in flexible and expandable light-waveguide (DEFEW). The DEFEW sensor has very wide frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 3 MHz and extremely high strain resolution. It can measure the strain rate change during the high speed phenomena. The sensor has been applied to measurement of micro failure process of single filament embedded in resin matrix. Elastic waves related to fiber breakage and interfacial failure between fiber and matrix were clearly detected. Wavelet analysis shows the two major components with different frequency ranges. Short time FFT is also applied to understand the failure process of fibers. Waveforms and frequency spectrums depend on the fiber rigidity and interfacial property between fiber and matrix.

KEYWORDS: failure, fiber-optic sensor, strain measurement, carbon fiber, aramid fiber, glass fiber, epoxy resin, fiber breakage, short time FFT, wavelet analysis, Doppler effect.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-optic sensors, such as Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) [1], Fabry-Perot Interferometer (FPI) [2, 3], Brillouin Optical Time Domain Refractometer (BOTDR) [4] and Brillouin Optical Correlation Domain Analysis (BOCDA) [5], have been widely applied to structural monitoring of civil infrastructures, aerospace applications, ground transportation and maritime structures, in order to assess the structural integrity. Most of the previous works were demonstrated under the static or quasi-static loading conditions. Non-destructive techniques based on ultrasonic and acoustic emission (AE) monitoring are very effective tools for structural health monitoring. Fiber-optic sensors have been applied to measurement of dynamic pressure [6] acoustic detection [7, 8] and hydrophone [9, 10].

Recently, Kageyama et al. [11] have found new fiber-optic phenomena. It is “Doppler effect in flexible and expandable light-waveguide (DEFEW)” - the frequency of light wave transmitted through a curved waveguide is shifted by motion of the bended region. A new fiber-optic strain rate sensor for vibration/acoustic measurement has been developed based on our new finding. An extremely high sensitivity has been achieved in the very wide frequency range (0.1 Hz -3MHz). A heterodyne interferometer gives output signal which is proportional to the strain rate value detected by the sensor. The DEFEW sensor has been applied to damage detection of composite materials [11], crack monitoring of concrete structure [12] and flexible structure [13]. In the present paper, the high speed strain rate sensor is applied to fundamental understanding of micro failure process of a fiber embedded in polymer matrix.

DOPPLER EFFECT IN FLEXIBLE AND EXPANDABLE LIGHT WAVE-GUIDE

Principle

Consider the light wave transmission in a media with refractive index, n . The light wave with frequency f_0 emitted from a moving point A (light source) is detected at other moving point B (observer). The distance between points A and B changes from L to $L+dL$ during infinitesimal time interval dt . Doppler frequency shift f_D is observed at B by the observer,

$$f_D = -\frac{n}{\lambda_0} \cdot \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (1)$$

, where λ_0 is the light wavelength in a vacuum, and λ_0/n is the light wavelength in the media.

Next, consider an arbitrary light path (light-waveguide), Γ , as shown in Fig. 1. The path is flexible and expandable. It has finite overall length, L , and two ends, denoted as points A and B, respectively. An incident light from the one end A (light source) is transmitted through the waveguide and detected at the other end B (observer). When the waveguide moves or vibrates, the same equation as Eq. (1) is applicable,

$$f_D = -\frac{n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} \cdot \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (2)$$

, where n_{eq} is the equivalent refractive index of the waveguide and λ_0/n_{eq} is the equivalent length of light wave in the waveguide.

From a geometrical consideration, dL/dt is given by Eq. (3),

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = [\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{t}]_A^B + \int_{\Gamma} \kappa \cdot \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} ds \quad (3)$$

, where κ , \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{n} are the curvature, the velocity vector and the unit normal vector of the infinitesimal segment, ds , respectively, and \mathbf{t} is the unit direction vector defined at the end points A and B. (See Fig. 1.) The operation \bullet indicates inner product of two vectors.

From Eqs. (2) and (3), we obtain the following equation;

$$f_D = -\frac{n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} [\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{t}]_A^B - \frac{n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} \int_{\Gamma} \kappa \cdot \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} ds \quad (4)$$

This equation implies ‘‘Doppler effect in flexible and expandable light-waveguide’’. As a feature of sensors, output signal shall return to steady-state value when the external excitation is removed. It requests that the waveguide is elastic, or deformation is reversible.

Fig. 1 Flexible and expandable light-waveguide Fig. 2 Examples of circular loop sensors

Behavior of light wave traveling through the media is complex. Exact solution should be obtained by applying special theory of relativity, but the present result gives sufficient accuracy when motion of light-waveguide is much slower than the light speed.

Circular Loop Sensor

In the case of a circular loop sensor as shown in Fig. 2, the sensitivity of strain rate can be evaluated by integrating Eq. (4) on the strain rate field. For simplicity, the uniform strain rate field, $\dot{\epsilon}_x$, $\dot{\epsilon}_y$ and $\dot{\gamma}_{xy}$ is assumed on the integration path. In the case of N turns of loop with average radius, R_{av} , the theoretical frequency shift, f_D^{th} , is obtained. The shear strain does not effect on f_D^{th} .

$$f_D^{th} = -\frac{N\pi R_{av} n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} (\dot{\epsilon}_x + \dot{\epsilon}_y) = -\frac{N\pi R_{av} n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} (\dot{\epsilon}_1 + \dot{\epsilon}_2) \quad (5)$$

When the vibration source locates at the center of the circular loop, the theoretical frequency shift is given by Eq. (6), which is proportional to the displacement rate in the radial direction, $\dot{u}_r(R_{av})$, or average radial strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_{r,av} = \dot{u}(R_{av})/R_{av}$.

$$f_D^{th} = -\frac{2N\pi n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} \cdot \dot{u}(R_{av}) = -\frac{2N\pi R_{av} n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{r,av} \quad (6)$$

Setup of Measurement System

A laser Doppler velocimeter (LDV) is used to detect the frequency shift. Light source is He-Ne laser (output power; 1mW, wavelength. λ_0 : 632.8 nm), and heterodyne interference technique as shown in Fig. 3 is applied to the measurement in the present paper. An acousto-optical modulator (AOM) changes the frequency of the reference light source from f_0 to f_0+f_M ($f_M = 80$ MHz) in order to produce beating signals with frequency of f_D+f_M .

Fig. 3 Setup of measurement system

Table 1 Specification of optical loop fiber sensor
(diameter: 20 mm, number of turns: 10): Calculated values

		Frequency Range: 0.1 Hz - 3 MHz				
Frequency		10 Hz	1 kHz	10 kHz	100 kHz	1 MHz
Resolution	Strain Rate ($\mu\epsilon/s$)		0.44		4.4	44
	Strain ($\mu\epsilon$)	0.01	0.0001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001
Total Dynamic Range (dB)			160		140	120

The sensitivity of the optical circular loop sensor (average diameter: 20 mm, number of turn: 10) is calculated theoretically. By applying commercially available performance data of the LDV (Melectro, V1002) [14], the resolution and dynamic range were obtained and listed in Table 1. Extremely high resolution less than nano-strain (10^{-10}) is expected in the very wide frequency range from 1 kHz to 1 MHz. Low frequency vibration of 0.1 Hz is detectable with sufficient sensitivity. The resolution of the newly developed sensor is extremely superior to the other fiber optic sensors, such as FBG, whose resolution is around $1 \mu\epsilon$ ($1 \mu\epsilon = 10^{-6}$). The developed fiber-optic sensor covers the measurement range from conventional strain gauge to AE sensor.

EXPERIMENTS

Single filaments of high strength (HS) PAN based carbon fiber, high modulus (HM) PAN based carbon fiber, aramid fiber and glass fiber were embedded in epoxy resin (West System #101). Specifications of the fibers are listed in Table 2. Tensile test specimens, as shown in Fig. 4, were fabricated, and DEFEW sensor and a pair of conventional PZT AE sensors were attached to the specimen. Tensile load was applied to the specimen under the constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min, and time history of AE events and the incident AE waves were detected with the DEFEW and PZT sensors as shown in Fig. 5. After the tensile test completed, the damaged specimens were observed with laser microscope. An example of the photograph is shown in Fig. 6. The fiber breakage and debonding between fiber and matrix are clearly observed.

Table 2 Specification of fibers

Filament type	Designation	Diameter (μm)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (GPa)	Density (g/cm^3)
High strength (HS) carbon fiber	TOHO TR50S	7.0	240	5.0	1.82
High modulus (HM) carbon fiber	TOHO HS40	5.0	447	4.73	1.86
Aramid fiber	DuPont Kevlar49	11.9	130	3.0	1.45
Glass fiber	Asahi Fiber Glass RH600A	11.0	76	2.0	2.56

Fig. 4 Configuration of test specimen

Fig. 5 Setup of tensile test

Fig. 6 Microscopic view of fiber breakage

RESULTS

Detected AE Waveforms

Detected strain rate and strain waveforms for HS carbon fiber, HM carbon fiber, aramid fiber and glass fiber are shown in Figs.7-10, respectively. strain waveform is obtained by time integration. An advantage of the DEFEW sensor is capability of transient measurement of dynamic strain.

Fig. 7 Example of AE waveform emitted from breakage of HS carbon fiber

Fig. 8 Example of AE waveform emitted from breakage of HM carbon fiber

Fig. 9 Example of AE waveform emitted from breakage of aramid fiber

Fig. 10 Example of AE waveform emitted from breakage of glass fiber

Wavelet Analysis

Wavelet transform is applied to the strain versus time diagrams. The diagrams have two components in the high and low frequency range. The two components are clearly identified in the wavelet analysis, when a Bior wavelet is chosen as a mother wavelet. Results of the analysis are shown Figs. 11 and 12 in the case of breakage of HS carbon fiber.

(a) Strain waveform

(b) Frequency spectrum

Fig. 11 Result of wavelet analysis in high frequency range (HS carbon fiber)

(a) Strain waveform

(b) Frequency spectrum

Fig. 12 Result of wavelet analysis in low frequency range (HS carbon fiber)

Results of wavelet analysis in high frequency range of HM carbon fiber, aramid fiber and glass fiber are shown in Figs. 13-15, respectively. They show almost the same frequency characteristics with frequency range between 100 kHz and 400 kHz.

(a) Strain waveform

(b) Frequency spectrum

Fig. 13 Result of wavelet analysis in high frequency range (HM carbon fiber)

(a) Strain waveform

(b) Frequency spectrum

Fig. 14 Result of wavelet analysis in high frequency range (Aramid fiber)

(a) Strain waveform (b) Frequency spectrum
 Fig. 15 Result of wavelet analysis in high frequency range (Glass fiber)

Short Time FFT Analysis

Short time FFT is applied to the waveforms of HM carbon fiber, aramid fiber and glass fiber. Examples of the results are shown in Figs. 16 (a)-(d). Different AE events give slightly different frequency spectrum patterns (See Figs. 16 (a) and (b)). HM carbon fiber shows higher frequency peaks and wider frequency bands than aramid and glass fibers at the initial stage of failure process. The short time FFT results represent characteristics of failure process of fiber filaments.

These figures also show excellent performance of DEFEW sensor, which has extremely wide frequency range and enough sensitivity for AE waveform analysis.

(a) HM Carbon fiber (b) HM Carbon Fiber

(c) Aramid fiber (d) Glass fiber

Fig. 16 Results of short time FFT

DISCUSSION

Strain versus time diagrams and wavelet analysis indicate that AE wave of fiber breakage has sharp pulse of emission with wide frequency range from 100 kHz to 400 kHz. We detected the sharp pulses of emission at the failure of HS carbon fiber, HM carbon fiber, aramid fiber and glass fiber. The almost same frequency spectrums are obtained in these tests, but HM carbon fiber shows the sharpest pulse peak in the strain versus time diagram, on the contrary glass fiber shows bluntest pulse peak. The pulse peak might depend on the rigidity of fiber. The sharp pulse is followed by the oscillating wave with low frequency of around 1 - 4 kHz. The wave forms with low frequency might have some relations to the interfacial properties between fiber and matrix and the rigidity of fiber.

Results of short time FFT denote the different patterns of frequency versus time histories of different fibers. These figures represent excellent performance of the DEF EW sensor with very wide frequency range. The combined technique of DEF EW sensor and short time FFT might give us a new NDE perspective for diagnostics of structural integrity.

CONCLUSIONS

New fiber-optic strain rate sensor has been applied to measurement of micro failure process of single filament embedded in resin matrix. The fiber-optic sensor is based on Doppler effect in flexible and expandable light-waveguide (DEF EW). The DEF EW sensor has very wide frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 3 MHz and extremely high strain resolution. Theoretical sensitivity of the circular loop sensor is discussed.

High strength PAN based carbon fiber, high modulus PAN based carbon fiber, aramid fiber and glass fiber are embedded in the epoxy resin. The DEF EW sensor has been applied to measurement of micro failure process of the single filament embedded in the matrix under the tensile load. Strain versus time diagrams is obtained from the detected waveform data, and effects of fiber type and interfacial property on frequency spectrum are discussed. Wavelet analysis denotes that elastic wave of fiber breakage has sharp pulse of emission followed by oscillating wave with low frequency of around 1 - 4 kHz. The sharp pulse has wide frequency range from 100 kHz to 400 kHz and shows weak dependency on the type of fibers. Results of short time FFT shows the different patterns of frequency versus time histories of different fibers. The combined technique of DEF EW sensor and short time FFT might give us a new NDE perspective for diagnostics of structural integrity.

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